

THE IMPACT OF HUMAN CAPITAL ON FIRM PERFORMANCE: AN EXPLORATION OF INNOVATIVE CAPABILITIES AND GOVERNMENT SUBSIDIES OF LISTED CHINESE MANUFACTURING COMPANIES

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Abstract

This research seeks to examine the mechanism by which human capital affects the performance of publicly traded firms. Specifically, it focuses on the effects of innovation capacity and government subsidies in Chinese manufacturing enterprises that are listed on the stock market. The sample is drawn from A-share manufacturing businesses that are listed on the Shanghai and Shenzhen stock exchanges between 2015 and 2022 and have implemented employee stock ownership schemes. The research used a fixed-effects model and stepwise regression methods to determine that there is a notable inverse correlation between human capital and company performance. Additionally, it was shown that innovation capacity partially mediates the link between human capital and firm performance. Furthermore, the presence of government subsidies did not have an important effect on the link between human capital and the capacity to innovate. These results enhance comprehension of the development of business investment plans and the efficient deployment of human resources. They also serve as a crucial foundation for policymakers to make adjustments to current subsidy programs.

Keywords: Human Capital, Firm Performance, Innovative Capacity, Government Subsidies, Fixed Effects Model, Listed Chinese Manufacturing Companies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Human capital has emerged as a crucial element in the success and competitiveness of businesses in the present knowledge-driven economy. It is advisable for companies to make deliberate investments in human capital to enable employees to make substantial contributions to the firm's operations and decision-making processes. This, in turn, will lead to sustained improvements in firm performance and long-term growth (Braunerhjelm & Lappi, 2023; Noradiva Hamzah et al., 2022).

Enterprises must embrace a humanistic approach to innovation in order to attain sustainable development. It is important to acknowledge that workers are the main drivers of innovation inside the organization (Aljuboori et al., 2021).

In light of this context, the CSRC released the Guiding Opinions on the Pilot Implementation of Employee Stock Ownership Plans by Listed Companies in 2014. Since then, employee stock ownership plans have been steadily enhanced, offering valuable incentives and regulations for businesses.

In the year 2023 The manufacturing industry has announced the highest number of equity incentive plans among the listed companies in the A-share market, making up 70.87% of the total. This highlights the significant size of the manufacturing industry, the increasing need for skilled technical professionals in the process of transformation and upgrading, and the importance of equity incentives in attracting and retaining talent. Through the alignment of employee and shareholder interests, employee stock ownership plans have proven to be a powerful tool in fostering investment in corporate innovation. This, in turn, has a significant impact on the innovative capacity of enterprises (Zhai et al., 2023; Cheng et al., 2023).

Government R&D subsidies have become a crucial topic of interest for both the government and academia. The question of whether these subsidies can effectively encourage innovation and drive the transformation of industrial structure is at the forefront of discussions (Yuan & Zhu, 2020). It is important to highlight that when developing subsidy policies, the government should carefully consider the accuracy of the subsidies and the impact they have on encouraging innovation. This will ensure that the policies are effective and relevant (Yu & Wang, 2022).

Considering the intangibility and complexity of human capital, accurately measuring it remains a significant challenge (Wilson, 2021). Additionally, there is still a need for further research to expand and deepen our understanding of the relationship between human capital and firm performance. Optimizing the allocation of human resources within an organization can provide strong support and guarantee for innovative activities.

Innovative behavior is influenced by individual innovative tendencies and organizational environmental factors (Lee & Lim, 2018). Human capital plays a crucial role in the strategic assets of firms, although the impact on developing new products remains uncertain, as suggested by recent research (You et al., 2021).

Overall, it seems that current scholars have overlooked the potential synergy between employee stock ownership plans and the field of human capital. This study delves into China's manufacturing industry and examines the effects of human capital on firm performance following the implementation of an employee stock ownership plan. By analyzing the mechanisms at play, this research aims to contribute to the existing literature and address any gaps in knowledge. This will provide insights into the mechanism of the relationship between human capital, firm performance, and innovation capacity. It aims to enhance our understanding of the effect of government subsidies in achieving effective incentive effects.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Human Capital and Firm Performance

The theory of human capital highlights the crucial importance of individuals' skills, knowledge, and abilities in fostering economic growth, organizational achievement, and competitive advantage (Schultz, 1960; Caire & Becker, 1967). It suggests that by enhancing individuals' skills and knowledge, economies can attain greater levels of productivity and competitiveness (Gruzina et al., 2021).

Human capital is a complex term that is difficult to quantify because it is intangible. There are three basic techniques to measuring human capital: the future profits approach, the cumulative cost approach, and the stock-of-education approach (Oxley et al., 2008).

The relationship between human capital and firm performance is complex and has a substantial influence on firm productivity, profitability, and value (Tran & Vo, 2020; Ali et al., 2022). The demographic aspects, such as education and experience, as well as the psychological components, such as tacit knowledge and dedication, of human capital, have a significant influence on the success of a corporation (Khan & Quaddus, 2018).

Employing individuals with entrepreneurial experience provides firms with the advantage of acquiring supplementary information and skills, hence enhancing production (Braunerhjelm & Lappi, 2023). Andersén's (2019) research provides evidence that company-specific human capital, which is customized to suit a business's own environment and requirements, has a positive correlation with firm success.

However, the influence of human capital on performance might differ considerably based on the firm's operating environment, industry, and market dynamics. Consequently, researchers have advocated for doing additional studies that are tailored to unique contexts in order to comprehend the impact of various settings on the relationship between human capital and performance (Khan & Quaddus, 2018; Sisodia et al., 2021). To summarize, the following theories are put forward:

H1: Human capital has significant effect on firm performance.

2.2. Definition and Role of Innovative Capabilities

Technical innovation theory aims to provide an explanation for the occurrence of technical innovation, including the factors that drive it, its effects on the economy and society, and the processes by which it spreads and evolves (Wei et al., 2023).

According to Limaj & Bernroider (2019), in order to produce superior innovation results, business organizations should strive for a well-balanced cultural makeup as a consistent driving strategy for sustainable corporate success. It is important to consider that the success of employee stock ownership schemes in promoting innovation is influenced by the caliber of the workforce and the kind of ownership (Sun & Liu, 2023).

Firm innovation capability refers to a firm's capacity to consistently advance and grow in the areas of technical innovation, institutional innovation, and managerial innovation (Lin & Peng, 2009). More precisely, it encompasses capabilities related to knowledge, technological innovation, and management, as identified by Camisón-Haba et al. (2019). These capabilities are crucial for companies to create innovative products, processes, and services, and to sustain a competitive edge in the market.

The sum of the effects of human capital and other forms of capital, the incorporation of both internal and external human capital inside the company, and the influence of entrepreneurial human capital all play crucial roles in strengthening the firm's potential to innovate (Sun et al., 2020; Li & Liu, 2018).

The correlation between a firm's ability to innovate and its overall performance is impacted by several factors, such as R&D investment, product innovation, management innovation capability, and innovation strategy (Wu et al., 2017; Wei et al., 2019; Yan, 2021). Moreover, research has shown that human capital incentives can greatly strengthen the connection between innovation capability and operational efficiency in enterprises (Zhang, 2019).

Additionally, there is a sequential logical relationship between high-performing human resource practices, intellectual capital, and the independent innovation capability of enterprises (Li et al., 2015). This relationship highlights the role of innovation capability as a bridge and connector in this process. Thus, the following theory is suggested:

H2: Innovation capability mediates the relationship between human capital and firm performance.

2.3. Definition and Role of Government Subsidies

Policy intervention theory is a significant field within economics that examines how governments impact economic activity, such as innovation behavior, by implementing different policies and measures (Song et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023).

Government engagement in technological innovation often involves encouraging firms to engage in technical research and development (R&D) and innovation activities via financial subsidies, tax incentives, and R&D assistance (Huang et al., 2019; Yuan et al., 2022).

Zhang and Ren (2020) shown that government subsidies have a substantial impact on enhancing the amount of investment in human capital for company innovation. Furthermore, the provision of government subsidies has a beneficial moderating impact on the correlation between businesses' expenditure in R&D and their success in innovation, as stated by Lou et al. (2023).

Nevertheless, the consequences of government subsidies are not fixed, and they have varying effects on the ability of enterprises to innovate based on their ownership, geographical location, industry, and stage of development (Wen & Huang, 2020; Gu, 2019).

It is worth mentioning that there are research that indicate government subsidies might potentially hinder businesses' innovation. Government subsidies might potentially result in enterprises engaging in excessive investment and increasing staff redundancy (Peng & Wang, 2018).

Additionally, subsidies may induce firms to prioritize quantity over quality in their innovation efforts, as they focus on obtaining subsidies rather than improving the overall innovation quality (Li & Zhen, 2016). To summarize, the following theory is put forward:

H3: Government subsidies play moderating role in the relationship between human capital and innovation capacity.

The conceptual framework describes the interconnections between human capital, innovation capacity, firm performance and government subsidies. The conceptual framework of this study is shown in Figure 1.

Fig 1: Proposed Research Framework

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Sources of Data

This study uses the CSMAR database to acquire secondary data on economic and financial research. The database is constructed in accordance with globally acknowledged standards and tailored to the Chinese context, ensuring the data's high quality and applicability (Xia & Wang, 2022). Annual reports of listed firms, which are periodically released corporate documents, serve as a significant source of financial and operational information for many stakeholders (Alduais, 2022).

3.2. Methods of Data Collection

In 2014, employee stock ownership plans were officially introduced into China's securities market as a significant institutional initiative. This study focuses on a sample of manufacturing companies that initially issued employee stock ownership plans in A-shares listed on the Shanghai and Shenzhen stock exchanges between 2015 and 2022. Given the particularity of the regulations in the Chinese stock exchange market, the criteria for selecting the sample include:

- 1) "ST" (Special Treatment) is a distinct stock identifier used in the Chinese stock market. ST firms are companies that face operational challenges or financial issues. These firms may engage in excessive surplus management to manipulate profits and comply with listing rules. Consequently, the mentioned sample firms are excluded from consideration (Chi et al., 2020).
- 2) Excluding example firms that lack accounting and financial information. After removing the missing values from important variables, we got a total of 3983 imbalanced panel datasets from 643 A-share manufacturing businesses registered on the stock market.

3.3. Variable Measurement

Table 1 provides an inventory of the measuring techniques used for all the variables examined in this research. This research identifies net profit growth, operating income growth, and return on equity (ROE) as the often used evaluation indicators when creating the performance assessment criteria for employee stock ownership plans in listed manufacturing businesses. This research selects ROE as the primary indicator to completely assess a company's corporate performance, since financial indicators may objectively and immediately measure performance and provide trustworthy statistical evidence (Ricordel & Majlath, 2019).

This research examines the human resources of a company as a valuable asset or investment and quantifies changes in human capital using established accounting rules and financial data. This research specifically utilizes the employee education spending ratio as an objective metric, as established by Ortega-Lapiedra et al. (2019) and Kim & Go (2020). The primary justification for this decision is the Opinions on the Management of the Extraction and Use of Enterprise Employee Education Funds, which was issued by the Ministry of Finance of China in 2006. The objective of this policy is to standardize the extraction and utilization of enterprise employee education funds, with the goal of fostering the advancement of employee education and training, as well as improving the professional expertise and overall competence of employees (Sun et al., 2008).

In order to assess the overall performance and efficiency of firms in the process of technological innovation, this study employs innovation capacity as a mediating variable and a quantitative measure of R&D investment expenditures. This study aims to impartially evaluate the impact of government subsidies on firms' innovative behaviors and their potential effects on market competition and economic welfare. It achieves this by precisely quantifying the number of government subsidy line items in the annual reports of listed companies (Wang & Zhao, 2023).

Table 1: Variable Definitions and Measurement

Variable Nature	Variable Name	Variable Measurement
Dependent Variable	Firm Performance	Net profit/average balance of shareholders' equity
Independent variable	Human Capital	(Labor Union Expenses + Employee Education Expenses)/ Gross Operating Revenue
Mediator Variable	Innovation Capacity	Proportion of R&D investment in operating revenue for the year
Moderator Variable	Government Subsidy	Amount of government subsidies obtained in the year

3.4. Estimation Models

Fixed effects models reduce the effects of omitted variable bias by accounting for individual characteristics that remain constant over time. This reduces the impact of dynamic misspecification, enhances estimation efficiency, employs adaptive instrumental variable methods, and conducts bias correction and testing (Haan, 2020). This work developed a multivariate regression model while accounting for individual fixed factors. In order to examine the impact of human capital on the performance of manufacturing enterprises (H1), a

model was developed:

$$\text{Firm Performance}_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{Human Capital}_{i,t} + u_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

In model (1), the explanatory variables $\text{Firm Performance}_{i,t}$ denote the return on equity, respectively, for firm i in year t . The explanatory variable $\text{Human Capital}_{i,t}$ represents the human capital of firm i in year t . α_0 stands for the intercept term, α_1 stands for the estimation parameters, u_i denote the fixed effects at the level of the firms, respectively; $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ denotes the residual term.

The Baron and Kenny (1986) causal stepwise regression technique is often used to find primary predictors and identify mediators. In order to examine the mediating role of innovativeness in the relationship between human capital and business performance (H2), a model is developed:

$$\text{Innovation Capacity}_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Human Capital}_{i,t} + u_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Firm Performance}_{i,t} = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1 \text{Human Capital}_{i,t} + \lambda_2 \text{Innovation Capacity}_{i,t} + u_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

To identify moderating effects, it is essential to create an interaction term, which is the result of multiplying the independent and moderating factors. The inclusion of the interaction term is essential as it allows us to examine how the combined effect of the independent and moderating factors influences the dependent variable.

To examine the moderating influence of government subsidies on the relationship between human capital and firms' innovation capacity (H3), researchers created a moderating analytical model. This model includes an interaction term between human capital and government subsidies, which was added to model (2).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Innovation Capacity}_{i,t} = & \eta_0 + \eta_1 \text{Human Capital}_{i,t} + \eta_2 \text{Government Subsidy}_{i,t} \\ & + \eta_3 \text{Human Capital}_{i,t} \times \text{Government Subsidy}_{i,t} + u_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.1. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Table 2 presents the results of the descriptive statistical analysis, providing a comprehensive overview of the central tendency, variation, and distribution range of the variables within the sample.

Specifically, the study encompasses a sample of 3,983 firms, with an average corporate performance value of 0.088, indicating a moderate positive trend. However, the standard deviation of 0.105 points to a certain degree of dispersion within the data. Moreover, the minimum performance value of -0.38 reflects potential losses among some of the sampled firms, while the maximum value of 0.381 illustrates significant disparities in the performance levels of listed manufacturing firms in China.

In terms of the core explanatory variable of human capital, the mean value is 0.133 with a standard deviation of 0.132. The minimum value is 0, suggesting that some firms did not invest in human capital in certain years, while the maximum value of 0.69 indicates considerable differences in human capital investment across firms. This underscores a pronounced disparity in the degree of human capital investment among listed manufacturing firms in China, highlighting the potential for enhancement.

Regarding innovative capacity, the average value is 5.029, which denotes a relatively high overall level. Nonetheless, the large standard deviation and the broad range from 0.150 to 22.610 suggest a high degree of variability in innovation capabilities among firms.

By contrast, the mean value for government subsidies is 16.482, which, coupled with a relatively smaller standard deviation, indicates a more stable distribution, ranging from 9.642 to 20.791. These statistical outcomes provide an essential empirical foundation for researchers to further analyze the relationships between the variables.

Table 2: Data Description and Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std	Min	Max
Firm Performance	3983	0.088	0.105	-0.380	0.381
Human Capital	3983	0.133	0.132	0.000	0.690
Innovation Capacity	3983	5.029	3.738	0.150	22.610
Government Subsidy	3983	16.482	1.872	9.642	20.791

4.2. Correlation Analysis

Table 3 provides the Pearson correlation coefficients, which indicate the degree of link between the variables, which allowed the researcher to understand the depth of their relationship. There exists a modest inverse relationship between the success of a firm and its human capital.

Despite the coefficient's tiny absolute value, it implies that a loss in firm performance may be somewhat linked to a reduction in human capital. Conversely, a rise in human capital may not considerably enhance firm performance.

In addition, it is important to point out that a specific inverse relationship exists between innovation capability and firm performance. This discovery may call into question the prevailing belief that innovation capability invariably enhances firm performance. Conversely, an innovation capability-human capital correlation of some degree exists, indicating that the development of human capital may contribute to the advancement of firms' innovation capabilities.

Furthermore, a negative correlation of some degree exists between government subsidies and human capital; this may indicate that enterprises' human capital requirements are not adequately accounted for in the allocation of government subsidies.

Nevertheless, a positive correlation has been observed between government subsidies and the innovation capacity and performance of businesses. This suggests that government subsidies continue to contribute to the improvement of innovation capacity and business performance to some degree.

Table 3: Results of Correlation Analysis

	Firm Performance	Human Capital	Innovation Capacity	Government Subsidy
Firm Performance	1			
Human Capital	-0.04	1		
Innovation Capacity	-0.137	0.203	1	
Government Subsidy	0.113	-0.084	0.087	1

4.3. Fixed-effects Model Results

The fixed effects model's findings are shown in Table 4. With a coefficient of -0.188, the research discovered that the human capital of manufacturing firms significantly negatively affects company performance in Model 1, which was obtained by applying the fixed effect model to the regression analysis. This finding suggests that rather than increasing company performance, improving human capital actually decreases it. In the meanwhile, this coefficient's standard error is 0.031, indicating a good degree of accuracy in the estimate findings. Additionally, the statistical significance of the negative impact of human capital on company performance is further supported by the p-value of 0, which is significantly lower than the significance threshold of 0.05. It is noteworthy to consider that the dependent variable's model has limited explanatory power, as shown by the low R-squared value of 0.052. However, the F-value of 16.219 suggests that the entire model fits the data really well. In conclusion, despite various restrictions, there is still a considerable negative influence of human capital on the firm performance of Chinese listed manufacturing enterprises, which validates Hypothesis 1.

Stepwise regression is a statistical technique that is often used to discover crucial mediators and predictors. The present investigation used the stepwise regression approach to examine the potential mediating effect of innovativeness between human capital and firm performance.

The findings from Model 2 indicate that innovation capacity is significantly and positively influenced by human capital, as indicated by the coefficient of 7.953. Compared to Model 1, this model has a greater standard error of 1.653; however, the P-value remains at zero, suggesting that the observed effect remains statistically significant. Furthermore, an increase in the R-squared value to 0.143 indicates that the model is now better able to account for variations in the dependent variable. The F-value of 13.955 provides additional evidence that the model fits the data more accurately.

The coefficient of human capital in Model 3 is 0.075, indicating a modest beneficial effect. Conversely, the coefficient of the mediating variable, innovation capacity, is -0.014, suggesting a negative association between the improvement in innovation capability and the decline in business performance. The standard errors for both human capital and innovation ability are minimal, and the t-values indicate that the impacts of both factors are statistically significant. Furthermore, the R-squared value has increased to 0.121, suggesting that the model's ability to explain the data has been substantially improved. The F-value of 23.617 is the greatest among all the models, indicating the superior overall fit.

The researcher concluded that innovation capacity partially mediates the relationship between human capital and company performance based on the aforementioned findings. Additionally, the researcher determined that the influence that mediates accounts for 69.13% of the overall effect using the Sobel test. The Bootstrap test yields trustworthy estimates and conclusions even in cases when the raw data do not fit the normal distribution.

The results of the Bootstrap test are shown in Table 5, where the statistically significant adverse effect is indicated by the first observed coefficient, *bs_1*. The effect remains consistent within the 95% confidence interval, providing more evidence of its substantive and statistical importance and supporting the earlier findings. In conclusion, there is evidence to support Hypothesis 2 that the innovation capacity of Chinese listed manufacturing businesses acts as a moderator between human capital and firm performance.

Table 4: Results of Fixed Effects Models 1-4

Model	Variable	Coefficient	std. err.	t	P-value	R Square	F Value
1	Human Capital	-0.188	0.031	-6.160	0.000	0.052	18.786
2	Human Capital	7.953	1.653	4.81	0.000	0.143	13.955
3	Human Capital	0.075	0.029	-2.540	0.011	0.121	23.617
	Innovation Capacity	-0.014	0.002	-9.360	0.000		
4	Human Capital	6.876	1.600	4.300	0.000	0.087	8.374
	Government Subsidy	0.081	0.027	2.970	0.003		
	Human Capital *Government Subsidy	0.428	0.376	1.140	0.255		

Table 5: Results of Bootstrap

	Observed Coefficient	Bootstrap std. err.	z	P> z	Normal-based [95% conf. interval]
<i>_bs_1</i>	-0.022	0.004	-5.26	0.000	(-0.030 -0.014)
<i>_bs_2</i>	-0.010	0.013	-0.76	0.444	(-0.035 0.015)

The variables of human capital and government subsidies, together with their interaction terms, were included by the researcher in Model 4. With an R-squared of 0.087, the model has broad explanatory power. The model is mostly acceptable, as shown by the F-value of 8.374. In particular, the coefficient of government subsidies is 0.081, demonstrating a positive influence once again, while the coefficient of human capital is 6.876, suggesting that it has a considerable positive effect on innovation ability. The interaction term's coefficient, however, is 0.428, and although it is positive, its p-value of 0.255 suggests that the interaction affect is not statistically significant. Thus, Hypothesis 3 is rejected because government subsidies in China's listed manufacturing businesses do not significantly moderate the relationship between human capital and innovation ability.

5. DISCUSSION

This research paper undertook a comprehensive analysis of the relationship between human capital and firm performance within publicly traded Chinese manufacturing companies, focusing specifically on the impact of employee stock ownership plans. The study's findings

offer crucial insights into the interplay among government subsidies, human capital, and innovation capacity. Initially, the study established a statistically significant inverse correlation between human capital and firm performance. This finding may seem paradoxical given the prevailing belief that investing in human capital enhances organizations' competitiveness and market performance (Khan & Quaddus, 2018; Sisodia et al., 2021). However, this discovery could potentially be attributed to unique contextual factors within China's manufacturing industry. For example, excessive allocation of resources toward human capital might not necessarily result in a proportional increase in productivity. Alternatively, the prolonged payback periods associated with such investments could impede immediate positive effects on performance (Jordão & Almeida, 2017).

Moreover, the study found that innovation capability acts as a mediator in the relationship between human capital and firm performance (Fu, 2020). This suggests that while initial investments in human capital may not directly impact firm performance, they can ultimately benefit long-term performance by enhancing innovation capability. This highlights the crucial role of innovation in driving sustained organizational prosperity (Li et al., 2015).

Furthermore, the study analyzed the effect of government subsidies on the correlation between human capital and innovation capacity. Despite the prevailing belief that government subsidies enhance firms' innovation capacity (Lou et al., 2023), this study did not find substantial evidence to suggest that government subsidies moderate the relationship between human capital and innovation capacity. This observation implies that existing subsidy policies may need further refinement to more effectively stimulate firms' innovative endeavors (Wen & Huang, 2020; Gu, 2019).

6. CONCLUSIONS

The following key findings emerge from this study:

- 1) Chinese manufacturing companies listed on stock exchanges demonstrate a negative correlation between investment in human capital and firm performance. This observation underscores the importance for firms to consider the nuanced relationship between human capital investment and firm performance when devising investment strategies.
- 2) Innovation capability partially mediates the relationship between human capital and firm performance, suggesting that enhancements in innovation capability may yield long-term returns on investments in human capital.
- 3) The limited evidence supporting the role of government subsidies as moderators in the relationship between innovation capacity and human capital suggests a need for manufacturing firms to reassess and adjust their current subsidy policies.

The study's sample is confined to publicly traded companies within the Chinese manufacturing sector, potentially limiting its generalizability across industries and national contexts. Future research should explore similar relationships that extend beyond specific industries and cultural

contexts. Additionally, efforts should be made to develop more effective policy instruments that incentivize organizations to invest in human capital and innovation.

Furthermore, further investigation could delve into the specific effects of different types of human capital investments on organizational operational effectiveness. Additionally, research is needed to determine the most effective approach to balancing immediate expenses with long-term gains.

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